

On Model Based Adaption of Deep Drawing Processes to Increase Process Stability and Resource Efficiency

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Abstract

In industrial deep drawing processes, stochastic fluctuations and disturbances in the manufacturing can result in a decreasing overall equipment effectiveness (OEE). The sensitivity to a fluctuation in component quality is further intensified in car body manufacturing due to complex geometries with small radii and the processing of high strength steels. The resistance to negative influences is referred to as resilience. This work presents and evaluates various smart stamping approaches that enhance the resilience of deep drawing processes. The focus is on the prediction of optimal press settings based on the incoming mechanical material properties. The mechanical material properties and component quality are continuously measured and fed into a model for analyzing the effects of fluctuations and disturbances on product quality through a feedback loop. Due to the ability to autonomously adapt to fluctuating environmental conditions and the automatic feedback, the meta model is considered as a digital twin.

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1 Introduction

In the European Union, nearly 13 million jobs are directly and indirectly dependent on the automotive industry [1]. To remain internationally competitive, there is immense cost pressure on production. In connection with the increasing importance of sustainable production, resource efficiency is gaining significance. High resource efficiency is advantageous in terms of overall equipment effectiveness (OEE) and CO₂ footprint. The OEE is a metric that measures the efficiency of production equipment by indicating the percentage of planned production time that is actually used to produce high-quality output [2]. Current challenges in the deep drawing of car body components include high geometric complexity, the processing of high strength steels for lightweight design, and the avoidance of lubricants for ecological reasons, which leads to reduced process stability. The lower the process stability, the more sensitive the reaction to stochastic variations in manufacturing conditions, such as incoming material properties, temperature, the continuity of a zinc coating on the blank and the resulting friction, or the positioning of the sheets in the tool. The more sensitive the reaction to stochastic variations, the more defects, such as splits, wrinkles, or springback, occur in the formed components. Smart stamping approaches can increase process stability in deep drawing [3]. This conference paper presents and evaluates various smart stamping approaches, with a focus on predicting optimal process settings based on the incoming mechanical material properties [4].

2 Smart stamping

Smart stamping approaches help increase the resilience of the deep drawing process. It is possible to classify them based on their degree of automation, see Figure 1. By means of a camera system, which evaluates the

component quality after forming, scrap can be automatically sorted out so that no defective components are sent to the customer. In this approach, the complexity is comparatively low and no information about the cause of the defect is required. However, it should also be considered that this approach does not control or impact production but rather automates a 100 % quality control. This approach does not affect the OEE, but it can, at most, result in saving the labor costs for an employee performing quality control manually. Additionally, there are no known cause-effect relationships here, which means that the current process will not be improved, and there will also be no opportunity to draw conclusions for future manufacturing processes from process adjustments. This is the reason why it is more advantageous to adjust the press settings after each stroke for the next stroke, based on the resulting component quality, as elaborated in [5]. This system measures the material inflow at the flange. If a tolerance range is exceeded, the gap between the die and the blank holder is adjusted for the next stroke. In this context, it is referred to as production control rather than process control. The advantage, once again, is that no cause for the defect needs to be known. However, the challenge is that only fluctuations that follow a trend over many strokes can be compensated for. Individual or few outliers cannot be compensated for by such a system, which iteratively adjusts the gap between the die and the blank holder after each stroke.

Figure 3: Smart stamping approach classified by grade of automation.

Another approach is to equip the tool with sensors, e.g. piezoelectric force sensors in the tool or material inflow sensors at the flange, which provide process data during the stroke [6]. Combined with a reference data set, defects can thus be avoided in real time and during the stroke. One way to control the material flow in real time is using actuators, which influence the surface pressure between the die, the blank, and the blank holder via a control loop. This approach avoids defects regardless of their cause for each stroke before they occur and therefore increases material efficiency even better than the two approaches presented before. In the context of real time control during the stroke, the data provided by the sensors during the stroke play an essential role, which is why the selection of the sensor, and its position are of particular importance. Studies on this can be found in [7]. One approach currently under research is the implementation of a holistic digital twin, including a feedback loop, so that not only the press settings but also the algorithm for predicting the optimal press settings adapt to changing environmental conditions. The approach presented below can be classified as an intermediate step between pure condition prediction and the long-term smart stamping vision. It includes nondestructive material testing systems and will be further discussed in the next chapter.

3 Predicting optimal press settings based on the incoming mechanical material properties

This smart stamping approach is based on preliminary investigations by [8] and [9], where the basic concept of predicting the optimal press settings before the stroke based on incoming material properties was introduced. What these approaches lack is the implementation of a holistic digital twin of the deep drawing process. This additionally includes a methodical approach to evaluate the sensors and their position, and a reliable and automated assessment of component quality based on these sensors. Furthermore, the system presented in this work includes two feedback loops. On one hand, the prediction of press settings based on the incoming material

properties is correlated with the component quality, and thus, the prediction algorithm is updated every production lot. On the other hand, when leaving a defined tolerance range of the incoming material properties, the material card of the Finite Element (FE) simulation is adjusted. This way not only does the algorithm adjust the press settings, but the meta model itself also adapts to changing environmental conditions. A basic flow chart of this approach is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Flow chart for predicting the optimal process settings before the stroke.

The approach also distinguishes between the short stroke cycle, and the longer meta cycle. The stroke cycle corresponds to the duration of a full 360° rotation of the crankshaft in a mechanical eccentric press. This would correspond to a cycle time of 3 s for example, with a stroke rate of 15 strokes per minute (SPM). The meta cycle includes the feedback loops as well as preliminary investigations using digital tools such as FE simulations and sensor eligibility η [7]. It is not feasible to calculate this for each stroke new, but a suggested time span for the meta cycle could be one cycle per production lot or one cycle per month. The temporal differentiation between stroke and meta cycle in this approach is another differentiating feature compared to existing approaches. The limitations in predicting optimal process settings before the stroke arise when the accuracy of the FE simulation model is insufficient to reliably simulate the sensors, thereby making the calculation of eligibility η ineffective. Furthermore, predicting the optimal servo curve or the optimal blank holder force (BHF) profiles based on the mechanical properties of the incoming sheet is not effective if the calibration of the nondestructive material testing system is inadequate. The implementation of this described digital twin brings increased complexity but also offers advantages that the previously presented approaches do not bring. For example, the cause of defects is known and can be corrected, instead of just addressing the symptoms, i.e., the defects.

The approach presented in this chapter comes closest to the vision of Smart Stamping. In this vision, the quality data of the incoming coil are provided 100 % by the supplier and can be used by the forming company. The cut sheets are equipped with a QR code or a comparable tracking and tracing system, which also includes information about which coil they come from. A reference to the FE simulation and the material card of the FE simulation is also included in the tracking and tracing system. Any sensor data measured before, during, or after forming is automatically added to the database of the individual part. Monitoring the condition of the press, the used tool kinematics, and the current tool status is also referenced. All of this information is available in a detailed dashboard via browser and app for the machine operator and in an abstracted form for the production manager. If a defect occurs, the affected parts can be precisely identified. In addition, all data is available to identify and understand the cause of the error. This way, the OEE and resource efficiency are maximized in the Smart Stamping vision, see Figure 5.

Figure 5: The Magna Cosma Smart Stamping press shop

4 Summary

Stochastic fluctuations in production conditions can be particularly disadvantageous to deep drawing processes if they are not designed to be resilient. Smart stamping approaches can achieve a higher process stability by increasing resilience. In this work, different approaches with different levels of automation are presented and evaluated. There are already systems that automatically detect and reject defective components, adapt the production process after each stroke for the next stroke, and control the process in real time during the stroke. In addition to that, the prediction of optimal press settings based on incoming material properties is particularly discussed in this work. If the component quality is measured after forming, for example, through material inflow, feedback loops can be implemented to update the digital twin.

5 References

- [1] De Vries, S., 2023, The Automobile Industry - Pocket Guide 2023/2024, ACEA - European Automobile Manufacturers' Association, p.5-9
- [2] Focke, M., Steinbeck, J., 2018, Steigerung der Anlagenproduktivität durch OEE-management, Springer Gabler Wiesbaden
- [3] Allwood, J.M., Duncan, S.R., Cao, J., Groche, P., Hirt, G., Kinsey, B., Kuboki, T., Liewald, M., Sterzing, A., Tekkaya, A.E., 2016, Closed-loop control of product properties in metal forming, CIRP Annals 65.2, p.573-596
- [4] Wolter, B., Dobmann, G.: Micromagnetic Testing for Rolled Steel, 9th European Conference on NDT in Berlin, ECNDT 2006, proceedings, Th.3.7.1
- [5] Thaddaeus, S., Henri, P., 2021, Adjustable Balancing Block for Closed Loop Die Control, WO2021141819A1
- [6] Barthau, M., Liewald, M., Held, C., 2017, Improved Process Robustness by Using Closed Loop Control in Deep Drawing Applications, J. Phys. Conf. Ser. 896(1), p.012040
- [7] Jung, R.O., Seper, C., Juricek, C., Bleicher, F.: Sensor integration for process control in deep drawing, The 27th International ESAFORM Conference on Material Forming in Toulouse, 2024, Materials Research Proceedings 41, p.1399-1407
- [8] Kim, H., Gu, J. C., Zoller, L., 2019, Control of the Servo-Press in Stamping Considering the Variation of the Incoming Material Properties, IOP Conf. Ser. Mater. Sci. Eng. 651(1), p.012062
- [9] Jung, R.O., Bleicher, F., Krall, S., Juricek, C., Lottes, R., Steinschütz, K., Reiningger, T., 2023, Cyber Physical Production Systems for Deep Drawing, ASME. J. Manuf. Sci. Eng. 145(10), p.101006